

Decoding Mucin O-Glycan Recognition by Commensal Bacteroides: Structural and Functional Insights

VG Correia^{1,2}, RL Costa^{1,2}, F Trovão^{1,2}, A Candeias^{1,2}, CF Juchem^{1,2}, A Di Maio³, T Feizi³, W Chai³, Y Liu³, AL Carvalho^{1,2}, BA Pinheiro^{1,2}, AS Palma^{1,2,3}

1. UCIBIO Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry/Department of Life Sciences, School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal; 2. Associate Laboratory i4HB, Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal; 3. Glycosciences Laboratory, Department of Metabolism, Digestion and Reproduction, Imperial College London, United Kingdom

b.pinheiro@fct.unl.pt

The mucus layer covering intestinal epithelial cells is rich in heavily O-glycosylated proteins known as mucins [1]. Both commensal and pathogenic bacteria in the gut exploit these mucin O-glycans in distinct ways. However, the molecular mechanisms by which O-glycans modulate the interaction between bacteria and the human host need elucidation. Notably, the commensal species *Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron* and *B. caccae* exhibit increased mucin O-glycan-degrading activity under low-fibre dietary conditions, which has been linked to an increased susceptibility to infection [2,3]. In this study, we present the characterisation of newly identified glycan-binding proteins from modular enzymes from these bacteria. These proteins are encoded by co-regulated gene clusters known as polysaccharide utilisation loci (PULs), which specifically target defined glycan structures [2]. Using sequence and structural bioinformatics analyses, we identified several candidate glycan-binding proteins for high-throughput expression and ligand screening. Structural studies using X-ray crystallography, combined with microarrays of human mucin-type glycoproteins and sequence-defined glycans [4–6], have revealed the molecular basis for recognising mucin O-glycan structures, including truncated core O-glycans, which are often overexpressed in cancer. Following these discoveries, we are characterising the associated catalytic domains for determining their activities as mucinases with novel O-glycan and peptide selectivities. Overall, this work offers new insights into the interaction between commensal bacteria and host glycans, with potential applications in cancer research.

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